

Earth is the biggest telescope for exploring events in extra dimensions and four dimensions

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Earth includes a combinations of spinors, waters and DNA in it's core. These elements help it to communicate with not only objects in four dimensional universe but also with objects in extra dimensions. By exchanging information and waves between earth and other cosmological objects in four or extra dimensions, the stability of material inside it will be vanished. Consequently, to re-produce stable conditions in core,some materials or waves are moved from core to surface of earth. These materials and waves lead to the emergence of earthquake. Thus, by analyzing waves of earthquakes, we can explore phenomenological events interior of extra dimensions.

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